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STUDY OF RESILIENCE IN FOREIGN MEDICAL STUDENTS DURING MARTIAL LAW IN UKRAINE

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Summary. Ogorenko V. V., Shusterman T. Y., Nikolenko A. E., Kokashynskiy V. O., Allfrid R. **STUDY OF RESILIENCE IN FOREIGN MEDICAL STUDENTS DURING MARTIAL LAW IN UKRAINE.** – *The Dnipro State Medical University; e - mail: viltord.koka16@gmail.com.* According to the recommendations of the World Health Organization, the preservation and promotion of youth health is one of the priority areas for the further development of practical medicine in the 21st century. Due to the ongoing war in Ukraine for the third year, the study of factors influencing psychological resilience among the student youth has gained particular importance. A particularly vulnerable group consists of students who have come from abroad to study. The aim of the study was to examine the state of resilience and its levels among international students who were pursuing higher medical education during the war in Ukraine. The study surveyed 69 students from the international faculty of Dnipro State Medical University, enrolled in the 4th (35 individuals) and 6th (34 individuals) years. The Brief Resilience Scale was used to assess levels of psychological resilience. Overall, the study shows a predominance of a moderate level of resilience among students in both groups, both in terms of the mean score and its prevalence. Similar results were found when comparing the indicators between male students in both groups, although 4th-year male students had a statistically significantly higher level of resilience, although it still corresponded to the moderate level. Meanwhile, among female students, no statistically significant difference was found in the average score, which corresponded to the moderate level of resilience, while there was a statistically significant predominance of a low level of resilience in the 4th-year group. The results obtained should be taken into account when planning and implementing psychoeducational and preventive measures for students, particularly in the context of the war in Ukraine.

Key words: resilience, international medical students, martial law, Ukraine.

Реферат. Огоренко В. В., Шустерман Т. Й., Ніколенко А. Є., Кокашинський В. О., Аллфрід Р. **ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ РЕЗИЛЬЄНТНОСТІ СТУДЕНТІВ-МЕДИКІВ ІНОЗЕМНИХ ГРОМАДЯН ПІД ЧАС ВОЄННОГО СТАНУ В УКРАЇНІ.** Згідно з рекомендаціями Всесвітньої організації охорони здоров'я, зберігання та підтримка здоров'я молоді є одним з пріоритетних напрямків подальшого розвитку практичної медицини у ХХІ столітті. Через війну, що триває в Україні вже третій рік, питання вивчення факторів психологічної стійкості (резильєнтності) серед студентської молоді набуває особливого значення. Особливо уразливим контингентом є здобувачі, що приїхали навчатись з - за кордону. Метою дослідження було вивчення стану резильєнтності та її рівнів у іноземних

студентів, які здобували вищу медичну освіту під час війни в Україні. Було обстежено 69 здобувачів вищої освіти Дніпровського державного медичного університету міжнародного факультету, які навчались на 4-му (35 осіб) та 6-му (34 особи) курсах. Для оцінки рівнів психологічної стійкості була використана коротка шкала резильєнтності (The Brief Resilience Scale). Загалом дослідження демонструє переважання середнього рівня резильєнтності серед студентів обох груп, як за середнім значенням показника, так і за поширеністю. Схожі результати були виявлені при порівнянні показників між студентами чоловічої статі обох груп, однак, представники 4-го курсу мали статистично значуще вищий рівень резильєнтності, хоча він також відповідав середньому рівню. Водночас, серед студенток жіночої статі не було виявлено статистично значущої відмінності за середнім показником, який відповідав середньому рівню резильєнтності, тоді як за поширеністю низького рівня резильєнтності спостерігалось статистично значуще переважання в групі 4-го курсу. Отримані результати слід враховувати при плануванні та проведенні психоосвітніх та профілактичних заходів для студентів, зокрема в контексті війни в Україні.

Ключові слова: резильєнс, іноземні студенти - медики, воєнний стан, Україна.

Introduction. According to the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO), the preservation and promotion of youth health is one of the priority areas for the further development of practical medicine in the 21st century [1].

Education in higher medical institutions is a specific type of activity associated with high levels of mental and physical stress. A particularly vulnerable group is students who have come from abroad to study, due to changes in their usual lifestyle, cultural differences, high emotional stress, language barriers, and so on [2].

The ongoing war in Ukraine, now in its third year, has brought the issue of studying the factors of psychological resilience among student youth into particular focus. According to research, 15% of international students have decided to stay in Ukraine for study and residence even during the war [3].

The issue of resilience has attracted significant attention from both international and Ukrainian researchers. Resilience is a complex, dynamic, and multidimensional set of qualities that determine a person's ability to overcome life's difficulties, successfully adapt, and continue development in difficult and dangerous conditions [4].

The relevance of this topic for the current situation in Ukraine is determined by the need to support and restore internal balance (physical, psychological, psychophysiological, etc.). Inadequate timing of preventive measures, early diagnosis, and correction of psychopathological disorders increases the risk of transforming subclinical conditions into clinically defined manifestations by 2.7 times [3]. Therefore, studying psychological resilience and the ability to cope with stress among international students is a priority scientific area.

Aim. To investigate the state of resilience and its levels among international students pursuing higher medical education during the war in Ukraine.

Methods. The study involved 69 students from the international faculty of Dnipro State Medical University, enrolled in the specialty 222 "Medicine." The participants were divided into two groups based on their academic year. The 4th-year group consisted of 35 individuals (15 men and 20 women), while the 6th-year group had 34 individuals (18 men and 16 women). No statistically significant difference was found between the groups in terms of gender ($p = 0.41$).

The Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) was used to assess the levels of psychological resilience [5].

The research was conducted in strict accordance with the principles of bioethics, in line with the Helsinki Declaration on "Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Participants," developed by the World Medical Association, the "Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (UNESCO) [6, 7].

Data processing was carried out using the Statistica 6.1 software (StatSoft Inc., serial number AGAR909E415822FA) and the MedCalc Statistical Software trial version 23.0.2 (MedCalc Software Ltd, Ostend, Belgium; <https://www.medcalc.org>; 2024). For indicators with distributions different from normal, non-parametric statistical methods were used (median and 1st–3rd quartiles (Me [Q1; Q3]) for presenting the indicators and the Mann-Whitney test for comparing results between groups. Homogeneity of groups by qualitative characteristics was

tested using the chi-square test [8]. Differences were considered statistically significant if the result had a p-value < 0.05.

Results. An analysis of the age indicators and personal resilience levels in both groups of participants was conducted, and the results are compared. The findings are presented in tabl. 1 and fig. 1.

Table 1

Indicators of Personal Resilience in Both Groups (in points)

	4th-year group n=35	6th-year group n=34	p
Age	22.0 [22.0; 24.0]	24.0 [24.0; 26.0]	p<0.01
Personal Resilience	19.0 [15.0; 22.0]	18.0 [17.0; 20.0]	p=0.39

When comparing the indicators in both groups, a statistically significant difference was found in age, which was due to the study design and the inclusion of 4th and 6th-year students. The personal resilience score in both groups was at a moderate level, and no statistically significant difference was found between the groups for this indicator.

Fig. 1 Level of Personal Resilience in Both Groups

When examining the qualitative indicators in both groups, the most common level of personal resilience was the moderate level. However, no statistically significant difference was observed between the two groups based on these indicators.

Notably, a high level of personal resilience was present among 9% of the 4th-year students, while it was absent among the 6th-year participants.

An analysis of the indicators and their comparison among male students was conducted, and the results are presented in tabl. 2 and fig. 2.

Table 2

Indicators of Personal Resilience Among Male Students (in points)

	4th-year group n=15	6th-year group n=18	p
Age	22.0 [21.0; 24.0]	25.5 [24.0; 27.0]	p<0.01
Personal Resilience	22.0 [18.0; 24.0]	18.0 [17.0; 19.0]	p<0.05

When studying the male students in both groups, a statistically significant difference in age was found, which was due to the inclusion of students from different academic years. The personal resilience score among male students was at a moderate level. Additionally, a statistically significant difference was observed in the resilience score, with 4th-year male students having a higher personal resilience score (p<0.05).

When examining the qualitative indicators, no statistically significant difference was observed between the two groups; in both groups, the moderate level of personal resilience predominated.

In the sample of male students, the previous trend remained, with a high level of personal resilience observed only among 13% of 4th-year students.

An analysis of the indicators and their comparison among female students was conducted, and the results are presented in tabl. 3 and fig. 3.

Fig. 2 Level of Personal Resilience Among Male Students

Table 3

Indicators of Personal Resilience Among Female Students (in points)

	4th-year group n=20	6th-year group n=16	p
Age	23.0 [22.0; 24.0]	24.0 [23.5; 24.5]	p=0.07
Personal Resilience	17.0 [14.0; 20.5]	19.0 [17.5; 21.0]	p=0.28

The study of female students showed no statistically significant difference in the indicators between the groups. The personal resilience score among female students was at a moderate level.

Fig. 3 Level of Personal Resilience Among Female Students

Note: * - $p < 0.05$

When examining qualitative indicators between the two groups, a statistically significant difference in the moderate level of personal resilience was observed, with a higher prevalence among 6th-year female students. In the 4th-year female student group, a low level of personal resilience predominated, while in the 6th-year group, the moderate level prevailed.

In the female sample, a high level of personal resilience was found only among 5% of the 4th-year female students.

Overall, the study shows that the moderate level of resilience predominated among students in both groups, both in terms of the mean value of the indicator and its prevalence ($p > 0.05$). Similar results were found when comparing the indicators between male students in both groups, although 4th-year male students had a statistically significantly higher level of resilience, which also corresponded to a moderate level. Meanwhile, among female students, no statistically significant difference was found in the average score, which corresponded to the moderate level of resilience, while a statistically significant predominance of low levels of resilience was observed in the 4th-year group.

The prevalence of adaptation disorders, according to literary sources, among the student population ranges from 5.8% to 61.4%. These disorders lead to reduced work capacity, impaired academic adaptation and performance, as well as a decrease in students' quality of life [2]. In a

study conducted in several Chinese medical educational institutions involving 4,754 students, 25.0%, 29.7%, and 15.3% reported anxiety, depression, and symptoms of maladjustment disorders, respectively [9]. According to the results of our study, female students in their 4th year of study with predominantly low resilience levels can be considered at risk for developing burnout syndrome [10, 11], using maladaptive coping strategies, and experiencing maladjustment disorders [3].

Conclusions

1. The level of resilience in both groups was found to be moderate, with no statistically significant differences between them.
2. A high level of personal resilience was found only in 9% of 4th-year students, while no students in the 6th-year group showed such a level.
3. The obtained results should be considered when planning and conducting psychoeducational and preventive measures for students, particularly in the context of the war in Ukraine.
4. For the risk group identified in the study, in addition to psychoeducational and preventive work, psychocorrective measures should be implemented to prevent maladjustment disorders and burnout.

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Внесок авторів/ authors' contribution:

- Огоренко В.В.: концепція дослідження, загальне керівництво
Ніколенко А.С.: концепція дослідження, загальне керівництво, написання статті, формування висновків
Шустерман Т. Й.: концепція дослідження, загальне керівництво, написання статті,

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Кокашинський В. О.: статистична обробка, аналіз результатів, написання статті, формування висновків

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RESEARCH INTO PAIRED CASES OF RARE PATHOLOGIES IN PAEDIATRIC ORTHOPAEDICS AND TRAUMATOLOGY

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Summary. ¹Protsaylo M. D., ¹Zubnina Yu. O., ¹Hrehk A. G., ¹Svystun R. V., ²Korol V. V., ¹Hoshchynskiy P .V. **RESEARCH INTO PAIRED CASES OF RARE PATHOLOGIES IN PAEDIATRIC ORTHOPAEDICS AND TRAUMATOLOGY.** - ¹I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, ²CNCE “Ternopil City Children's Municipal Hospital”; e-mail: protsaylo@tdmu.edu.ua. The law of paired events, observed in various medical settings, refers to the phenomenon where, after witnessing a rare or exceptional event, similar occurrences tend to follow within a short period. This trend is particularly evident in fields such as paediatric orthopaedics and traumatology. The objective of the research is to investigate such paired events, particularly focusing